

Life and Reliability Examination of Internal Gear and External Gear Contact in Gear Mechanisms

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Abstract

Gear mechanisms are indispensable mechanisms used in many machines as power and motion transmission elements. What is expected from gear mechanisms is that they can achieve a high cycle rate in a small area and function for a long time. In this study, safety, life and reliability comparisons of gear mechanisms in terms of root and flank safety in internal and external gear contact were carried out using analytical calculations and the KissSoft program. A modular calculation tool for machine element design, optimization, and verification in accordance with international standards is called KISSsoft®. The program is also available for evaluating the internal gear. Within the scope of this study, calculations were made within the scope of ISO 6336 standards. The contributions of internal gear contact, which is widely used in mechanisms such as harmonic reducers and planetary systems, to life and reliability are examined. In internal gear contact, there are large differences in contact ratio and load distribution due to form factor. Studies on internal gear mechanisms are much less than those on external gear mechanisms. Especially in internal gear mechanisms, profile modification is very open to work. In this study, the effects of profile shifting and changing the pressure angle in the tooth involute structure, as basic gear modifications, on gear strength and life were examined. The effects of these elements on the gear in internal and external gear contact were examined and optimum design parameters were tried to be obtained. As a result, it has been seen that the internal gear contact is much more efficient than the external gear contact, both in terms of space coverage and strength. The manufacturability of profile modifications in the design of real gear mechanisms was also evaluated in the study.

Keywords: Gear mechanism, reliability analysis, KissSoft, internal gear, external gear

1. Introduction

Gear mechanisms work with conjugate motion and enable the torque to be increased with this conjugate movement of the gear systems. Among the power and motion transmission mechanisms, they are the most used mechanisms due to their high efficiency and ability to be used reliably at all power and speed values. However, their costs may be higher compared to other mechanisms [1]. Internal and external gears can be used in gear systems [2]. The use of internal gears is especially common in planetary gear systems [3]. Gear tooth geometry of external and internal involute gears can be described by the same equations, except the following rule: The number of teeth is given positive in external gears and negative in internal gears. However, studies show that different stress values occur in internal and external gear systems. [4]. The most common types of damage in gear applications are fractures at the base of the teeth or wear on the side surfaces. For this reason, the strength control of gears is examined from two aspects. One is the tooth root strength and the other is the side surface strength. When sizing gear wheels, they are required to provide these two strength values with sufficient safety. It is checked whether the stress values obtained in all strength calculations of the gear wheels are lower than the safety stress values of the material [5]. Contact fatigue is an important failure mode of the gear [6]. In this mechanism, wear occurs because of deformations caused by high surface pressure between tooth surfaces gripping each other [7].

Repetitive stresses cause a material to fail at stresses lower than its yield point. Fatigue is the term used to describe this kind of material failure. Cracks that occur gradually and are often tiny and small are what lead to the failure [8]. Generally speaking, fatigue is a significant issue that impacts any moving or structural part [9]. Wöhler is credited as being the first to do methodical experimental research on fatigue strength; the focus of his studies was the fracture of railway car shafts. [10]. Wöhler identified a material property in these experiments that is now known as the fatigue limit. [11]. S-N curves, which depict the relationship between load cycles up to failure and stress range applied in a structure, can be used to illustrate fatigue life. By giving the engineers these curves, they can more reliably estimate the design stress levels [12].

One of the most hazardous types of gear failure is caused by tooth root bending fatigue. Consequently, a crucial component of gear design is defining gear bending fatigue strength precisely. In actuality, a correct estimation of the component SN curve is necessary in order to evaluate a gear component [13].

To prevent the fatigue failure caused by bending of the tooth root, designers utilize multiple standardized calculation techniques, such as ISO 6336-3 and ANSI/AGMA 2001. They state that the tooth root stress is compared to the limit value for the desired life in order to evaluate a gear pair [14]. In this study, a comparison of life expectancy values for a gear pair system in case of using internal and external gears was carried out theoretically. A comparison of the life analysis of the involute profile internal and external gear contact, which is widely used in structures such as planetary and harmonic gear systems, compared to two external gear contacts, was carried out.

2. Experimental Studies

2.1. Determining of Tooth Root Safety and Flank Safety Values

In the study, tooth root safety and flank safety values were calculated by KISSsoft® AG Program. KISSsoft® is a modular calculation program for the design, optimization and verification of machine elements according to international standards. It was used the ISO 6336 standard at gear calculations. Following equations were used in the program.

$$\sigma'_i = \frac{F_t}{b \cdot m} \cdot Y_f \cdot Y_s \cdot Y_\beta \cdot K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_{F\beta} \cdot K_{F\alpha} \leq \sigma_{FP} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), F_t is the tangential force, b is the tooth width, and m is the module value. Y_f is the form factor, Y_s is the stress correction factor, Y_β is the helix angle factor, The factor K_A , called application factor, is used to take into account the effect of external overloading. It depends on the application. The dynamic factor K_V considers the internal dynamic loads. The factors $K_{F\beta}$ and $K_{F\alpha}$ are used to model the uneven load distribution in the contacts along the face width and in the transverse direction and σ_{FP} is the permissible bending stress. The limit value of tooth-root stresses should preferably be derived from material test using gears as test pieces, σ_{FG} ,

$$\sigma_{FP} = \frac{\sigma_{FG}}{S_{Fmin}} \quad (2)$$

Minimal Root safety values can be determined as follow.

$$S_{Fmin} = \frac{\sigma_{FG}}{\sigma_{FP}} \quad (3)$$

Minimal flank safety values can be determined as follow.

$$\sigma_H = Z_B \cdot \sigma_{HO} \cdot \sqrt{K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_{H\beta} \cdot K_{H\alpha}} \leq \sigma_{HP} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{HO} = Z_H \cdot Z_E \cdot Z_\epsilon \cdot Z_\beta \cdot \sqrt{\frac{F_t}{d_1 \cdot b} \cdot \frac{u+1}{U}}$$

In Eqs. (4), σ_H is the actual Hertz stress, Z_B is the single gear contact factor, σ_{HO} is the nominal contact stress, $K_{H\beta}$, $K_{H\alpha}$ are tooth surface load distribution factors, σ_{HP} is the allowable surface stress, Z_H is the zone factor, Z_E is the elasticity coefficient factor, Z_ϵ contact ratio factor, Z_β Helix angle factor, d_1 is the pitch diameter, u is the ratio.

The formula for calculating the permissible contact stress σ_{HP} is given in Eq. (5).

$$\sigma_{HP} = \frac{\sigma_{Hlim} \cdot Z_{NT}}{S_{Hmin}} \cdot Z_L \cdot Z_V \cdot Z_R \cdot Z_W \cdot Z_X = \frac{\sigma_{HG}}{S_{Hmin}} \quad (5)$$

σ_{Hlim} is the fatigue strength for Hertzian pressure (N/mm²), Z_{NT} is the life factor, Z_L , Z_V , Z_R , Z_W and Z_X are the lubricant, lubrication speed, surface roughness hardness ratio and size factors. Respectively and σ_{HG} is the pitting stress limit (N/mm²)

The relation used to calculate the critical minimum flank safety S_{Hmin} value is given in Eq. (6)

$$S_{Hmin} = \frac{\sigma_{HG}}{\sigma_{HP}} \quad (6)$$

In order to compare internal and external gear contact in the program, only internal and external gear contact was created by keeping the number of teeth, profile shifting values and all gear modifications equal. Information about the selected gears is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Information about the selected gears

Model	Number of gear teeth Z_1-Z_2	Normal module	Pressure Angle	Helix Angle	Facewidth Z_1-Z_2	Profile Shift Coefficient X_1-X_2	Center Distance
External Gear Pair 1	14-41	2	20	20	40-30	0,3281 -0,5846	58 mm
Internal Gear Pair 1	14--41	2	20	20	40-30	0,3281 -0,5846	29,22 mm
External Gear Pair 2	14-41	2	25	20	40-30	0,3281 -0,5846	58 mm
Internal Gear Pair 2	14--41	2	25	20	40-30	0,3281 -0,5846	29,22 mm
External Gear Pair 3	14-41	2	20	20	40-30	0 -0,2567	58 mm
Internal Gear Pair 3	14--41	2	20	20	40-30	0 -0,2567	29,22 mm

Selected gear materials was 18CrNiMo7-6 case-hardened steel (ISO 6336-5 Figure 9/10 (MQ), Core hardness $\geq 25\text{HRC}$, Jominy J = 12mm < HRC2). The properties of materials are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The properties of gear materials (18CrNiMo7-6 case-hardened steel)

Surface hardness	Infinite life strength for tooth root stress (N/mm ²)	Fatigue strength for Hertzian pressure (N/mm ²)	Young's modulus (N/mm ²)	Poisson's ratio [ν]	Tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Yield point (N/mm ²)
HRC 61	430.00	1500.00	206000	0.300	1200.00	850.00

Selected design parameters (input rev., power and torque) are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Design parameters

Input rev (rpm)	Input power (kW)	Input Torque (Nm)
1480	7,5	48,39

Root and flank safety values are given in results and discussion sections. In addition, fatigue calculation was carried out according to the tooth root stress values calculated within the scope of the KISSsoft program. Required minimum safety values according to ISO standard are given in Table 4.

Table 4. Required minimum safety values according to ISO Standards

	$m \leq 0,5$	$m = 1$	$m \geq 2$
Min. Root Safety	0,43	0,85	1
Min. Flank Safety	0,6	0,9	1

2.2. Fatigue Calculation According to Wöhler Curves of Gears

Being able to accurately predict gear failure is an important element of achieving a reliable, lightweight gearbox. Among various gear failures, tooth root bending fatigue is considered the most dangerous as it means the entire gearbox stops working. In order to characterize a gear for this phenomenon, stress values reaching $3 \cdot 10^6$ or $6 \cdot 10^6$ cycle numbers are generally taken as basis as the

endurance limit [15]. Figure 1 shows the typical dimensionless S-N curve for several typical gear material proposed by ISO 6336-3[14].

Figure 1. Typical S-N curve according to ISO 6336

In the study, $3 \cdot 10^6$ cycle was defined as endurance limit of the gear material. σ_u is ultimate stress, σ_i is nominal stress value; the minimum life value can be obtained as follows [16].

$$\log[N] = 3 + 3,4771 \left[\frac{0,9 \cdot [\sigma_u] - \sigma'_i}{0,9 \cdot [\sigma_u] - [\sigma'_e]} \right] \tag{2.1}$$

σ'_e refers to the fatigue endurance of the gears and σ'_i refers to the tooth bending stress of the gear. Tooth bending stress calculations for external or internal spur and helical gears are obtained as follows according to the ISO 6336 standard.

$$\sigma'_i = \frac{F_t}{b \cdot m} \cdot Y_F \cdot Y_S \cdot Y_\beta \cdot K_A \cdot K_V \cdot K_{F\beta} \cdot K_{F\alpha} \tag{2.2}$$

Infinite life strength for tooth root stress (fatigue endurance of the gears) was taken from Table 2 and the tooth bending stress of the gear is taken from KISSsoft® calculation. The program obtains all factors and data from standards. This allows all account data to be included and the calculation to be made in a comprehensive and detailed manner.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Results of the Tooth Root Safety and Flank Safety

Root safety and flank safety values were given in Table 5.

Table 5. Root and flank safety values

Root Safety S_{fmin}	Z_1		Z_2	
	Root Safety S_{fmin}	Flank Safety S_{hmin}	Root Safety S_{fmin}	Flank Safety S_{hmin}
External Gear Pair 1	3,75	0,93	2,93	0,96
Internal Gear Pair 1	3,61	1,47	3,71	1,66
External Gear Pair 2	3,609	0,981	3,079	1,014
Internal Gear Pair 2	3,449	1,487	2,664	1,684
External Gear Pair 3	3,422	0,954	3,443	0,986
Internal Gear Pair 3	3,345	1,511	3,917	1,11

Considering the minimum safety coefficient values of the external pinion gear in the internal gear systems, it has been observed that it is at an unsafe level in terms of hertz stresses. However, safe values

were obtained in the internal gear systems. In addition, it is seen that the pressure angle and profile shifting ratios have a significant impact on the safety coefficients. Considering the tooth bottom safety values, the gears of both designs are at a safe level. When the power transmitted and all other factors are equal, the difference in safety coefficients is remarkable. It is clear that this will also affect gear life.

3.2. Results of the Fatigue Calculation

In order to perform the minimum life calculation safely, the limited life region was taken as the basis and it was assumed that the slope in this region continued in the long life region. The results of the theoretical logarithmic life values of gears is given in Table 6.

Table 6. Fatigue calculation results of the gears (cycle)

	External Gear Pair		Internal Gear Pair	
	LogN ₁ (Z ₁)	LogN ₂ (Z ₂)	LogN ₁ (Z ₁)	LogN ₂ (Z ₂)
Gear Pair 1	7,7512	6,4771	7,7115	6,5166
Gear Pair 2	7,7060	6,5254	6,6566	6,1263
Gear Pair 3	6,6570	6,6023	7,6312	6,5199

When tooth root bending fatigue values are examined, it was observed that there was a decrease in pinion gear (Z₁) in internal gear contact compared to external gear contact. Beside of this increase of the value in the gear (Z₂) is also noticeable. It is seen that the pressure angle and profile shifting ratios affect the safety coefficients as well as the logarithmic life values significantly. These values also affect contact ratios. In each gear design, the significant effects of the mentioned values on life and safety factors should be taken into consideration.

4. Conclusions

As a result of the study, it was seen that internal gear contact significantly reduces Hertz contact stresses both pinion and gears. In addition, it has been observed that internal gear contact reduces tooth root stresses, in the gear section. In the pinion, no significant decrease in tooth root stress was observed at the internal gear contact. This disadvantage in the pinion can be eliminated with the multi-planet structure in planetary systems. Additionally, in harmonic systems, the stress on the pinion can be reduced by enlarging it. It has also been determined that tooth root and surface pressure stresses directly depend on the pressure angle and profile shifting ratios.

Beside of this, the small space occupied by internal gears reduces the casting cost of the gear mechanism body. However, having a compact system requires extra attention to lubrication. In this study, ordinary gear contact was taken into consideration. However, internal gears are of great importance not only in ordinary gear contact, but especially in planetary reducer systems and harmonic systems (for example, cyclo drive). Considering the advantages of these systems, it is clear that more intensive research should be done on internal gear systems and the number of manufacturing of these systems should be increased.

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